

Implementation of Emergency Management in Local Governments in Ecuador:

Development and Resilient Communities

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1. Introduction

Local communities are the first row of preparedness when disasters strike. During the last decades there has been a deeper study and understanding of risk and disaster management through national institutions, international organizations, non-governmental organizations and academic programs. Along these lines, self-preservation and the willingness to protect human integrity, vital infrastructure and natural environment, have pushed people's capabilities to overcome adverse events.

Starting from the point that emergency management is an innovative academic field in upper middle-income economies like the Republic of Ecuador, South America (The World Bank, 2015), national action plans for risk and disaster management come from centralized institutions. However, local governments, in this case municipalities account with disproportionate qualified emergency management personnel, tools, infrastructure, coordination, and knowledge to prepare for, respond to, recover from, and mitigate impacts of crisis and emergencies (Yeletaysi, Ozceylan, Fiedrich, Harrald, & Jefferson, 2008).

The intention for the following research is to establish the need to institutionalize emergency management in municipal local governments in Ecuador. In order to build resilient communities, with active participation and involvement in the Emergency Management field. Furthermore, human security is a concern that must be tackled from bottom-up participation to decrease the levels of vulnerability in each community in the event of a disaster.

2. Objectives

- Outline the current status of Emergency Management in the country, the national institutions that support the system, and the constitutional framework that promotes Emergency Management as a policy of state.

- Acknowledge the role of local governments during an emergency and crisis, and the levels of involvement according to the territorial scope, as well as, the committee of risk management with the actors that are part of the committee in function of the incident scope.
- Study the implementation of emergency management in local governments, and present the case of the technical unit of emergency management in the Metropolitan City of Quito, and how this unit had helped to make the metropolitan district an awarded resilient city.
- Describe the municipal risk management unit as a technical unit of emergency management that will work closely with the community, and the committee of risk management to implement emergency plans for a disaster's phases.
- Employ the current management of emergencies and crisis per zone to promote emergency management in local governments, through capacity building in communities, and disaster opportunity to train local staff. This will generate community resilience, with a deeper understanding of vulnerability that follows recommendations and use the national frameworks and examples.
- Expose the contribution of emergency management to development policies and programs, and how community risk management improves sustainable development to break the cycle of poverty in an upper middle-income country.

3. Emergency Management in Ecuador

First, it is worth to notice that emergency management is known in the country as risk management. The maximum authority in this manner is the National Secretariat of Risk

Management (SNGR), which is coordinated by the Ministry of Security Coordinator. The SNGR mission is:

Leading the Decentralized National System for Risk Management to ensure the protection of people and communities from the negative effects of disasters of natural or human origin, through the creation of policies, strategies and standards that promote strategies to identify, analyze, prevent and mitigate risks to confront and handle events of disaster capabilities; as well as to recover and rebuild the social, economic and environmental conditions affected by any emergency or disaster.

The SNGR follows the constitutional articles 389 and 390 from the Constitution of 2008 of the Republic of Ecuador. Mentioted articles are postulated in the Title VII “The Good Way of Living System”, in the Chapter one “Inclusion and Equity”, Section nineth “Management of Risk” (Constitution of the Republic of Ecuador, 2008).

Even though, emergency management, or in this case risk management, has been institutionalized in the national system, local goverments barely acknowledge the management of emergencies, crisis and disasters in their municipal functions. This is a major concern because the spectrum of threats and hazards in the country change from province to province and even from canton to canton, which is an administrative and territorial division (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012)

3.1 The Role of Governments in Emergency Management in Ecuador

According to McLoughlin (1985) all levels of government are involved in emergency management, while some emergency responsibilities and functions are common to all sections, each level of government also has its own unique responsibilities and resources.

The National Decentralized System of Risk Management, through the committee of risk management, coordinates the role of governments in emergency management in Ecuador (SNGR, ECHO, UNISDR, 2012). According to the territorial level the committee of risk management (CGR) is conformed in national, provincial and cantonal levels, and it can be

coordinated in the parish level, or mechanisms of parish coordination can replace the committee (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012). Table 3.1.1 shows the committee's levels and the participating actors.

Committee of Risk Management National Actors	Committee of Risk Management Provincial Actors	Committee of Risk Management Cantonal Actors	Committee of Risk Management or Mechanisms of Parish Coordination
President of the Republic or his delegate	Provincial's Governor	Mayor	Chairman of the Parish Council
Secretary of the SNGR	Provincial's Prefect	Representatives of Municipal Enterprises	Political Lieutenant
National Secretariats (According to competence)	SNGR Provincial Director	Chief of the Municipal Risk Management Unit	Delegates of the Committees and Risk Management Networks
Coordinators Ministers	AME Provincial Representative	Cantonal Political Chief	Representatives of the institutions/agencies relevant in the Parish
Sectorial Ministers	Provincial Secretaries and Directors of the State Entities	Chiefs of Public Relief Agencies	Delegates of the Relief Agencies in the Parish
Commander in Chief of the Armed Forces	Senior officer of the Armed Forces in the Province	Chief of the Armed Forces in the Canton	Delegate of the Armed Forces in the Parish
Commander of the National Police	Senior officer of the Police in the Province	Chief of the National Police in the Canton	Delegate of the National Police in the Parish
AME President	President of the Provincial Federation of the Parish Councils	Cantonal Representative of the Parish Councils	Local representatives of NGOs registered in the SNGR
Other members at the discretion of the National CGR	Other members at the discretion of the Provincial CGR	Other members at the discretion of the Cantonal CGR	Other members at the discretion of the SNGR

Table 3.1.1 Territorial level and the Committees of Risk Management (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012)

As it is noted, the spectrum of the committees of risk management goes from national actors to mechanism of parish coordination (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012). Taking into account the perspective of community collaboration in emergency management, the municipal risk management unit is the bridge between the community participation and involvement with the higher institutions levels of risk management (Hennessy, 1998).

3.2 Emergency Management in Local Governments in Ecuador

A relative new acknowledgment of emergency management through the constitution and the SNGR gives the framework to upgrade the management of emergencies, crisis and disasters as a policy of state (SNGR, 2015). Nonetheless, the sustainable development of emergency

management must be generated with a bottom-up participation (Boughton, 1998). A central axis for the integration of national policies into the communities are the local decentralized autonomous governments, in this particular case municipalities (Boughton, 1998).

In order to implement policies, plans, programs and projects of prevention, mitigation, recovery, and reconstruction to reduce the risk and threats in a territory, the SNGR signs agreements of “Institutional Cooperation Framework” with the decentralized autonomous governments in each province (Ecuadorian Association of Municipalities [AME], 2013). Despite creating the institutional agreements, the implementation of technical units of emergency management in each municipality takes considerable time to be accomplished (SNGR, 2015).

An interesting example of an emergency management technical unit in a local government is the metropolitan directorate of risk management (DMGR) in the municipality of the Metropolitan District of Quito (MDMQ). The DMGR works together with:

- Metropolitan directorate of public safety.
- Metropolitan directorate of support to victims of violence.
- Metropolitan directorate of governance, the metropolitan police.
- Fire department of Quito.
- Metropolitan public company of logistics for security and coexistence.

All mentioned directorates are organized under the general secretariat of security and governance, which follows the lead of the metropolitan council and the mayor’s office (MDMQ, 2015).

The legal framework that supported the creation of the risk management unit is the municipal ordinance 0265 of September 14th, 2008. Such detailed document clarifies competences of the metropolitan system of integrated risk management of the Metropolitan

District of Quito and its components. Along these lines, the objective of the System is the following: “Public and private institutions, social organizations, international cooperation entities, must interact, coordinate, link and function systematically for the integrated risk management, allowing safeguard the security of people, property and infrastructure of the Metropolitan District of Quito” (MDMQ, 2008).

The risk management directorate that will come to assume the tasks of an emergency management technical unit is a significant example of institutionalization in the local government. Notwithstanding, the DMGR in the MDMQ is a unique case in Ecuador. This is due to the fact the city has been implementing a remarkable plan to build a resilient city (MDMQ, 2015). This effort made possible for the city to be part of the 100 Resilient Cities Network, initiative promoted by the Rockefeller Foundation (MDMQ, 2015). The objective of this initiative is to generate a strategy for a resilient city, which focuses on three benefits clearly identified (MDMQ, 2015):

- The city will learn and share the best practices and tools for urban resiliency.
- The city will focus on the barriers of urban resilience and global achievements of resilience.
- The city will lead the debate of urban resilience locally and globally.

Nonetheless, an equal level of risk management has not been achieved in other local governments in the country. Consequently, not all levels of government are entirely involved in emergency management in the event of a disaster.

3.3 The Municipal Risk Management Unit

The municipal risk management unit operates according to the community’s needs and coordinates actions with agencies and institutions to develop emergency plans, in order to

prepare for, respond to, recover from, and mitigate impacts of crisis and emergencies. At the same time, the municipal risk management unit incorporates mandates of national institutions in the cantonal level.

Local governments in emergency management have a range of different potential roles and can bring a wide range of resources to contribute to local responses to emergency management, such as: emergency response and disaster planning, strategic planning, infrastructure design and provision, civic leadership, and safer cities programs (Hennessy, 1998). Equally significant is the community participation and community involvement, Hennessy (1998) makes a distinction between these two:

Community participation is generally taken to mean that the community takes responsibility for all stages of the program including planning and implementation. Community involvement is used to refer to a less-ideal situation in which the community is asked to participate in a program that has already been designed by someone else, without consultation, and usually on the terms of (and possibly in the interests of) the outside designer rather than on the community's terms and in the community's best interests. (p. 12)

Even though this is a certain definition, it is necessary to understand that emergency management is a pioneer field in the country. For this reason, even in the idealistic community participation situation, where the parish coordination is responsible for all stages of the program is difficult to achieve. At the same time, community involvement as directed by the SNGR may not account for the community's best interests. Consequently, the interaction between the cantonal risk management unit and the community must be in two ways.

Diagram 3.3.1 Relationship between local government risk management unit and community

Similarly important is to acknowledge that the municipal risk management unit must coordinate actions with the mayor's office, municipal enterprises, cantonal political chief's office, public relief agencies, armed forces, national police, representative of the parish councils and other required members.

Moreover, the incident's scope may involve higher institutional actors in the provincial level and national level. However, the municipal risk management unit is the first institutional row to attend the crisis or emergency, and provide response. Likewise, this unit creates plans, establishes the recovery process, and mitigates the impacts of future events.

Diagram 3.3.2 Municipal Risk Management and actors during an adverse event

From the 221 cantonal decentralized autonomous governments in the country, 101 local governments have received qualified training to institutionalize emergency management technical units. Moreover, 70 of the cantonal governments have integrated risk management as part of their planning process, through the establishment of municipal risk management unit. Chart 1 shows the increase of municipal risk management units in the decentralized autonomous

governments, since, the management of emergencies, crisis and disasters was recognized as a policy of state (SNGR, 2015).

Chart 3.3.3 Percentage of municipalities with risk management units (SNGR, 2014)

Despite the increase of local governments with risk management units, municipalities lack full competency to manage risk and disasters as a part of their functions, as a result, the SNGR has opted to manage disasters and prepare emergency management personnel per zones (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012).

4. From zonal risk management to community risk management

The SNGR follows the premises of decentralization, autonomy and territorial planning to attend incidents, train personnel, and strengthen resilient capabilities. Therefore, the SNGR uses the establishment of zones proposed by the National Secretariat for Planning and Development (SENPLADES). According to SENPLADES (2008), zoning is proposed to facilitate space organization management, integrated planning and balance land use. The design of zones depends on the potential and limitations of the resources available. The basis for this process is the efficient care of the requirements and population's needs.

Zone	Structure
Zone 1	Esmeraldas, Carchi, Imbabura, Sucumbíos
Zone 2	Pichincha (Except Quito canton), Napo and Orellana
Zone 3	Cotopaxi, Tungurahua, Chimborazo and Pastaza
Zone 4	Manabí and Santo Domingo de los Tsáchilas
Zone 5	Santa Elena, Guayas (except Guayaquil, Samborondón and Duran), Los Ríos, Bolívar and Galápagos
Zone 6	Cañar, Azuay and Morona Santiago
Zone 7	El Oro, Loja and Zamora Chinchipe
Zone 8	Guayaquil, Samborondón and Duran
Zone 9	Quito Metropolitan District

Table 4.1 Territorial Organization, Zones with Provinces distribution

Hence, the zoning approach is a mechanism useful to strengthen local governments in the field of emergency management, and a tool to develop resilient communities. This takes into account that during a disaster, local emergency departments such as firefighters, volunteers from the Ecuadorian Red Cross, and local emergency staff work together with the SNGR personnel. This scenario can be used to train personnel and transmit to the community the knowledge and the need of emergency plans designed with the phases of mitigation, planning, response and recover.

Diagram 4.2 Risk Management Replica Effect

Even though zoning is a valuable approach to manage emergencies and crisis, it is required to create self-sustainable resilient communities. The context of each canton changes, and the threats differ highly from one canton to the other. For the sake of sustainable risk management the SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR (2012) recommend:

- a. Formation of an academic research network on vulnerability in Ecuador that supports the concerns of risk and vulnerability.
- b. Development of vulnerability studies and methodology.
- c. Creation of vulnerability indicators in institutions like the National Institute of Statistics and Census (INEC).
- d. Strengthen municipalities to perform studies and assessments with vulnerability tools and management of information.
- e. Design approaches and criteria for vulnerability analysis and emergency management in national and local institutions that direct these subjects.
- f. Enhance sustainability through an academic reflection about vulnerability and emergency management.

The purpose of these recommendations is to develop community oriented risk management by improvements on the current system to administer emergencies and crisis. They are based on territorial organization, current initiatives of municipal risk management units, agreements between local governments, role of governments in risk management, best practices in the Metropolitan District of Quito, and the constitutional framework as a policy of state.

5. Development and Resilient Communities

The study of development and disaster management is innovative, as how development helps to build resilient communities (Kapucu & Liou, 2014). Disaster management and

development encourages policy makers and managers to design development policies and programs to create opportunities for business and industry formation (Kapucu & Liou, 2014). These policies and programs address problems of economic cycles and recessions and consequences of financial crisis, and they have to prioritize the incidence and challenges of natural, man-made, technological, biological and chemical disasters, that can impact directly or indirectly the economic functions and community lives (Kapucu & Liou, 2014).

Considering that community resiliency is the community's capacity to absorb disturbance and re-organize into a fully functioning system (Cutter, Barnes, Berry, Burton, Evans, Tate, & Webb, 2008), development policies and programs must contemplate an integrated disaster and development framework that allows communities to anticipate, accommodate, and recover from the effects of an adverse event (Kapucu & Liou, 2014; Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [IPCC], 2012).

5.1 Current Development and Disaster Policies in the Country

The SNGR in Ecuador needs to implement the innovative disaster and development framework, based on the Strategic Framework for Risk Management in Ecuador, which is composed by the National Plan for the Development of the Good Living and the Security Agenda and Integrated National Security Plan (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012). As a general reference, the National plan for the Development of Good Living, with its objective No. 4, seeks to guarantee the rights of nature and promote a healthy and sustainable environment (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012). This objective includes Risk Management through policy No. 4.6, which promotes the need of reducing social and environmental vulnerability effects caused by natural and anthropic events that generates crisis and emergencies (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012).

Similarly, the Security Agenda and Integrated National Security Plan considers the Environmental and Risk Management approach (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012) that has the added component of risk reduction, response and recovery. Also, the National Plan for Integrated Security in the objective No. 4 emphasizes to reduce the vulnerability of people and nature to the negative effects of natural or anthropic events (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012). This objective includes the variable of risk management through the policy for the prevention and tackling of natural or anthropic disasters, and the policy to decrease the negative effects caused by environmental threats (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012).

5.2 Development policies, programs and the Municipal Risk Management Unit

Policies and programs are created in the higher institutional level, and implemented by national ministries, secretariats, agencies and departments. Notwithstanding, local governments must play a central role to transmit policies and programs, as well as, involve communities in sustainable development. As a matter of fact, community resiliency is an attainable feature of sustainable development (Kapucu & Liou, 2014), and resilient communities are generated through disaster readiness (Norris, Stevens, Pfefferbaum, Wyche & Pfefferbaum, 2008). As it was previously proposed, the municipal risk management technical unit will allow achieving disaster readiness in the community.

Therefore, the municipal risk management unit is the binding bridge between policy makers, managers and the community. Thus, the implementation of emergency management in local governments will contribute to the development and resilience of communities. The technical unit will identify four key elements that build community resilience: social vulnerability, existing environment and infrastructure, natural systems and exposure, and hazards mitigation and planning (Kulig, Edge, Townshend, Lightfoot & Reimer, 2013).

The Strategic Framework for risk management with its components the National Plan for the Development of the Good Living, the Security Agenda and the Integrated National Security Plan, as well as, the legal and regulatory framework for risk management in Ecuador composed by:

- The Constitution of the Republic of Ecuador.
- The Public and State Security Act.
- The Public and State Security Act Regulatory Decree.
- The Organic Code for Territory Organization, Autonomies and Decentralization (COOTAD).
- The Organic Code of Planning and Public Finances (COPLAFIP).

These are institutional elements that provide and guarantee the process by which a wide range of actors like state, private sector and civil society interact in the policy and technical aspects of risk and emergency management (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012; Kapucu & Liou, 2014).

The holistic approach to integrate disaster and development has been emphasized by policymakers and public managers in the country, and practiced by national institutions like the SNGR (Kapucu & Liou, 2014; SNGR, 2015). In consequence, the autonomous decentralized governments or cantons with risk management units increased from 2.26% in 2008 to 31.67% in 2014. Even though there is a significant increase in emergency management units in the country, the DMGR in the Municipality of the Metropolitan District of Quito is the only unit fully operational and competent to deal with adverse events. The rest of municipalities or autonomous decentralized governments in the country rely on the higher level of committees of risk management to affront emergencies and crisis.

5.3 Resilient Communities and Reduction of Vulnerability

Development practices and policies have decreased vulnerability and potential threats in the country (Kapucu & Liou, 2014; SNGR, 2014). Nonetheless, cantons and communities find themselves struggling to prepare and plan, mitigate, respond with skilled personnel, and recover financial and physical losses from disasters; that is in part from the lack of sustainable community development (Kapucu & Liou, 2014). One realistic characteristic of sustainable development is creating resiliency in the appearance of catastrophic events (FEMA, 2000). Therefore, communities need to create resiliency before a disaster as a method of reducing vulnerabilities and recovery costs after a disaster (Kapucu & Liou, 2014). It is known that effects of disasters are associated to poverty and degradation of natural land (Kapucu & Liou, 2014).

Communities with high levels of poverty are more vulnerable to disasters and its effects (Kapucu & Liou, 2014). The economic progress achieved through development policies and programs is disrupted when a disaster strikes. However, capacity building will create a culture of preparedness at individual, family, community, local government, private sector, and nonprofit organizations, which will improve the management of disasters to sustain the development accomplished. Thus, reducing vulnerability will contribute to break the cycle of poverty. Map 5.3.1 shows the vulnerability due to poverty in the country, from which it can be deduced the need to reduce vulnerability and strengthen local capacity to deal with crisis and emergencies. In addition, Chart 5.3.2 illustrates the evolution of poverty, since developing policies and programs that combine disaster management were put in place in the country.

Map 5.3.1 Vulnerability due to poverty (SNGR, ECHO & UNISDR, 2012)

Chart 5.3.2 Evolution of poverty (INEC, 2015)

Through the execution of choice and action, resiliency is built by communities, individuals and organizations (Kapucu & Liou, 2014). In the case presented, local governments in the country will play a central role to create resiliency and sustainable community development to deal with disasters. This perspective is shared by May (2013), who observed:

There are two important concepts that can lead to the creation of participation in resiliency efforts. The first is enacting some form of mandate on state and local governments, which focuses on reduction of hazards; while the second is extending planning efforts to identify common recovery goals in partnerships with all levels of the community. (p.128)

The municipal risk management unit will perform the mandate to reduce hazards, as well, prepare and plan, coordinate response, and recover from emergencies and crisis. In addition the emergency management unit will identify common goals with all actors in the community for a sustainable recovery.

6. Conclusion

In an upper middle-income country like Ecuador, emergency management has gained institutional recognition like a Policy of State. This provides the framework to design and build the current system of risk management. Consequently, the country is better prepared to affront emergencies and crisis caused by natural and anthropic threats. Nonetheless, there is the need to spread the improvements to the local governments to contribute to the process of resilient communities.

The National Secretariat of Risk Management has been in charged with implementing emergency management in the national level by considering the legal, regulatory structure, and the Strategic Framework for risk management in Ecuador. This allows for the SNGR to create institutional agreements with the decentralized autonomous governments in the cantons. This has resulting in the increase of municipalities with risk management units. However, it should be

noted that only the Direction of Risk Management in the Metropolitan District of Quito is fully functional and operational to manage emergencies and crisis. This scenario occurs due to the high levels of development in the Metropolitan District in comparison with the rest of country.

The key to strengthen local capabilities to affront adverse scenarios is to replicate the example of Quito, and to use disaster circumstances as opportunities to train local personnel. The current management of emergencies and crisis per zone is a remarkable opportunity to create community oriented emergency management, and institutionalizes the field in local governments. In this manner, capacity building that takes into account all sectors will generate community resilience. A necessary feature for sustainable development is to generate community resilience, with the purposes of maintaining progress achieved by developing policies and programs to reduce poverty, and to engage communities to participate in emergency plans.

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